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Radiometric Survey Of Radionuclides In Oilfield Chemicals And Products In Southern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Radiometric survey of radionuclides in oilfield chemicals and products with its associated radiological hazards in Southern Nigeria have been carried out using gamma spectroscopy. Fifty-three samples consisting of thirty-two solids and twenty-one liquids were randomly collected from facilities handling them. These samples were prepared following the ISO procedure and kept sealed in a Marinelli beaker for twenty-eight days to attain secular equilibrium before counting with thallium activated sodium iodide NaI(Tl) detector. The lowest to highest specific activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K , in solid samples are 0.03 ± 0.01 to 13.01 ± 3.06 Bqkg^{-1} , 0.03 ± 0.003 to 1.17 ± 0.09 Bqkg^{-1} and 3.87 ± 0.31 to 20.64 ± 7.71 Bqkg^{-1} respectively; similarly for the liquid samples are 0.31 ± 0.07 to 14.96 ± 3.17 BqL^{-1} , 0.09 ± 0.01 to 2.19 ± 0.16 BqL^{-1} and, 0.22 ± 0.02 to 109.63 ± 6.85 BqL^{-1} respectively. The activity concentrations of the samples were mostly within standard values except in Reverse Demulsifier, Triethylene Glycol, Hydrogen Sulphide Scavenger, Subsea Biocide and Scale Inhibitor whose activity concentration values for ^{40}K ranging from 86.20 ± 5.70 to 109.63 ± 6.85 BqL^{-1} ; also values for ^{238}U ranging from 6.60 ± 1.76 to 14.96 ± 3.17 BqL^{-1} ; and values for ^{232}Th ranging from 0.93 ± 0.07 to 2.19 ± 0.16 BqL^{-1} , significantly higher than UNSCEAR standard values of 27.6 BqL^{-1} for ^{40}K , 10BqL^{-1} for ^{238}U and 1BqL^{-1} for ^{232}Th . The radiological health hazard parameters determined from the activity concentration of the radionuclides using mathematical models were mostly within their safe recommended values. However, the elevated activity concentrations from the five samples show some radiological contamination and a potential for negative impact to worker, public and the environment over long term period.

Keywords: Radionuclides, oilfields, Spectroscopy, lifetime cancer, demulsifier

1. INTRODUCTION

The background ionizing radiation of the environment at normal condition is 0.011 $\text{mR}h^{-1}$ and is generally taken to be everywhere (EPA, 1996). The natural radioactivity of the atmosphere is due largely to ^{222}Rn (WNA, 2011) emitted by the minerals in the Earth's crust and in the hydrosphere, as well as to the radioactive products of the interaction of atmospheric gases and cosmic radiation. Certain rocks in hydrocarbon bearing formations are known to contain natural radioactivity. The determination of radionuclides from hydrocarbon produced from such formations through produced water samples (Avwiri et al., 2013); various oil and gas waste streams (Ononugbo et al., 2019); and oil pipe scale deposits (Azionu et al., 2019) have been reported from studies. These studies predominantly attributed the observed radionuclides to dissolved Barium and Radium salts mobilized in the well effluent flowing to the surface.

Exploration and Production of hydrocarbons involve three main phases which could be summarized as seismic evaluation of underground rock layers for hydrocarbon deposits; drilling of wells to connect the hydrocarbon reservoir to the surface; and the production of hydrocarbon through a surface facility. During the drilling and production phases several oilfield chemicals and products are injected into the wells and the facilities. However, studies in the radiological impact of these chemicals and

products remain limited. Lee (2009) investigated the biodegradation of synthetic base mud in marine sediments and the marine amphipod test attributed the population decline to severe toxicity after spiking the sediments. However, the presence or effect of Radon known to commonly evolve from mud systems (Jonas et al., 2018) was not considered and therefore could not conclusively eliminate the impact of ionizing radiation from the evolved radon as being a contributor to the observation made on the marine amphipod population. Nigeria reported 294 Metric Tons assorted oilfield chemicals injected for an annual crude oil production of 104,585 Metric Tons in 2018 (DPR, 2018). Considering the amount of bulk chemicals injected into the hydrocarbon production processes, the possibility exists that some portion of the radionuclides which are eventually identified and quantified in these studies are attributable to these chemicals.

Workers in the oil and gas industry may unknowingly be exposed to elevated levels of radiation due to the accumulation of naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORMs) in oilfield products or through their contact with oilfield chemicals and products having irradiation properties. Improper disposal or accidental release of oilfield chemicals containing radionuclide can contaminate soil, surface water, and groundwater resulting in radiation exposure to members of the host community. Radiation exposure could lead to acute health effects such as neurovascular syndrome for high doses and short duration (Hall and Giaccia, 2012). It could also cause chronic effects such as cataracts for moderate doses and long duration (Hammer et al., 2020). The objectives of this research are to determine radionuclides in samples of oilfield chemicals and products collected from the southern part of Nigeria and evaluate the radiological health risk parameters from those radionuclides using radiation models. This work helps in identifying radiologically hazardous chemicals, contributing to better environmental monitoring, pollution prevention, and improved remediation strategies.

The study area (Fig. 1) is the Southern Nigerian Coastal Oilfield Area which extends from the Bight of Bonny on longitude 8.0°E to the Bight of Benin on longitude 2.0°E; and overlaying 30 Km offshore the Atlantic Ocean up to 70 Km onshore Nigerian coastline. Facility A is an onshore warehouse at Onne Port, southeast Nigeria. Facility A is an onshore warehouse at Onne Port, southeast Nigeria, where drilling chemicals and products are stored in Lots identified by the names of the stored samples. Facility B is an onshore warehouse at Ladol Port, southwest Nigeria, where drilling chemicals and products are stored in Lots identified by the names of the stored samples. Facility C is an offshore warehouse at a Floating Production Storage & Offloading (FPSO) Terminal where production chemicals and products are stored in Lots identified by the names of the stored samples

Fig. 1: Geographic Information System map of the Study Area

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample Collection and Preparation

Thirty-two solid drilling chemical /product samples (Table 1) collected in black plastic containers from Onne and LADOL warehouses, were pulverized; oven dried at 110°C until they attained constant weight, then sieved to minus 30 mesh before 600g each of the samples were weighed into radon impermeable Marinelli beaker, sealed with a plastic tape to ensure air tightness. Also, twenty-one liquid samples (Table 2) one liter each, were collected in black plastic bottles. Sample containers were rinsed three times with sampled liquid to minimize contamination from any content of the sample container before samples were taken with at least 1% air gap left in the container for thermal expansion. 500 ml of liquid was measured using measuring cylinder and poured into a 500ml Marinelli beaker. The beaker was covered with the beaker lid and sealed properly to ensure that there is no room for escape for any radioactive gas. All sample were labelled with the sample number, weight of sample, density of sample, and date of encapsulation on a piece of masking tape placed on the lid, then kept for 28 days to establish secular equilibrium between ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and their progenies (Alam et al., 1999). Each sample was counted for 18000 seconds using Thallium activated Sodium Iodide, NaI(Tl) detector and the peak analysis was performed using SAMPO 90 software.

2.2 Gama Spectrometric Analysis

The Gamma Spectrometer System used for evaluating the activity concentration of the radionuclides is Thallium activated Sodium Iodide, NaI(Tl) detector Canberra manufactured P-type detector, model 802 (Serial Number: 13000850) with a preamplifier model 2002CSL (Serial Number: 13000742) connected to 16K Multi Channel Analyzer (MCA). This Gamma Spectrometer System used for this research work is available in the laboratory of National Institute of Radiation Protection and Research (Nigerian Nuclear Regulatory Authority), University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Table 1: Solid oilfield chemicals and products sampling plan

S/N	Location	Sample Code	Sample Size Collected	Sample Name	GHS Health Hazard
1	Warehouse, A (Onne)	BN _{1a}	400mL	Bentonite	Not classified
2		BN _{2a}	400mL	Bentonite	Not classified
3		BR _{1a}	400mL	Barite	Carcinogenicity
4		BR _{2a}	400mL	Barite	Carcinogenicity
5		CG _{1a}	400mL	Class G cement	Irritation
6		CG _{2a}	400mL	Class G cement	Irritation
7		BG _{1a}	400mL	Blasting Grit	Not classified
8		BG _{2a}	400mL	Blasting Grit	Not classified
9		PN _{1a}	400mL	Natural Polymer	Non-hazardous
10		PN _{2a}	400mL	Natural Polymer	Non-hazardous
11		PS _{1a}	400mL	Synthetic Polymer	Not available
12		PS _{2a}	400mL	Synthetic Polymer	Not available
13		TS _{1a}	400mL	Produced Sediment	Not available
14		TS _{2a}	400mL	Produced Sediment	Not available
15	Warehouse, B (LADOL)	CW _{1a}	400mL	Coffee Waste	Not classified
16		CW _{2a}	400mL	Coffee Waste	Not classified
17		BN _{1b}	400mL	Bentonite	Not classified
18		BN _{2b}	400mL	Bentonite	Not classified
19		BR _{1b}	400mL	Barite	Carcinogenicity
20		BR _{2b}	400mL	Barite	Carcinogenicity
21		CG _{1b}	400mL	Class G cement	Irritation
22		CG _{2b}	400mL	Class G cement	Irritation
23		BG _{1b}	400mL	Blasting Grit	Not classified
24		BG _{2b}	400mL	Blasting Grit	Not classified
25		PN _{1b}	400mL	Natural Polymer	Non-hazardous
26		PN _{2b}	400mL	Natural Polymer	Non-hazardous
27		PS _{1b}	400mL	Synthetic Polymer	Not available
27		PS _{2b}	400mL	Synthetic Polymer	Not available
29		TS _{1b}	400mL	Produced Sediment	Not available
30		TS _{2b}	400mL	Produced Sediment	Not available
31		CW _{1b}	400mL	Coffee Waste	Not classified
32		CW _{2b}	400mL	Coffee Waste	Not classified

GHS - Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals

The detector characteristics include: 76 mm diameter; 76 mm length with Resolution (FWHM): 7.274 KeV, Resolution @662 KeV: 7.5%, ⁶⁰Co @ 1.33MeV and Relative efficiency: 80%. The SAMPO 90 software program enables emission counts to be plotted against radionuclide energies and then, convert the peak width count information to specific activities (Bqkg⁻¹ or Bql⁻¹). Although Sodium Iodide resolution is lower than that of High Purity Germanium (HPGe), it does not require a very low temperature like HPGe for its operation. A Multi-Gamma Ray Standard (MGS6M315) was used to calibrate the NaI(Tl) detector.

Table 2: Liquid chemicals and products sampling plan

S/N	Location	Sample Code	Sample Size Collected	Sample Name	GHS Health Hazard
1	Production	OBm	1L	Oil-Based mud	Toxicity/Irritation
2	Facility, C	PCr	1L	Produced Crude	Carcinogenicity
3		PCo	1L	Produced Condensate	Carcinogenicity
4		CI ₁	1L	Corrosion inhibitor 1	Toxicity/Irritation
5		CI ₂	1L	Corrosion inhibitor 2	Toxicity/Irritation
6		SIo	1L	Scale inhibitor (oil)	Toxicity/Irritation
7		SIw ₁	1L	Scale inhibitor (water)1	Toxicity/Irritation
8		SIw ₂	1L	Scale inhibitor (water)2	Toxicity/Irritation
9		SB ₁	1L	Subsea Biocide 1	Toxicity/Irritation
10		SB ₂	1L	Subsea Biocide 2	Toxicity/Irritation
11		PB ₁	1L	Process Biocide 1	Toxicity/Irritation
12		PB ₂	1L	Process Biocide 2	Toxicity/Irritation
13		DB	1L	Diesel Biocide	Toxicity/Irritation
14		RD	1L	Reverse Demulsifier	Toxicity
15		DM	1L	Demulsifier	Toxicity
16		OS	1L	Oxygen Scavenger	Toxicity/Irritation
17		HS	1L	H ₂ S Scavenger	Corrosive/Irritation
18		TG	1L	Tri-ethylene Glycol	Toxicity/Irritation
19		AA	1L	Acetic Acid	Corrosive/Irritation
20		CD	1L	Crude-Oil Defoamer	Irritation
21		CS	1L	Chemical Solvent	Toxicity

GHS - Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals

Table 3: Radiological health hazard indices

S/N	Health Hazard Index	Computational Model	Source
1	Absorbed Dose Rate (D)	$D \text{ (}^n\text{Gyh}^{-1}\text{)} = 0.462C_{Ra} + 0.621C_{Th} + 0.0417C_K$	60nGyh ⁻¹ (UNSCEAR, 2000).
2	Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE)	$AEDE \text{ (mSvy}^{-1}\text{)} = D \times CC \times TC \text{ (hy}^{-1}\text{)} \times OF \times (10^3\text{mSv}/10^9)$	20mSvy ⁻¹ (Worker); 1.0mSvy ⁻¹ (Public); (ICRP, 1999; UNSCEAR 2000)
3	Annual Gonadal Equivalent Dose (AGED)	$AGED \text{ (mSvy}^{-1}\text{)} = 3.09C_{Ra} + 4.18C_{Th} + 0.314C_K$	≤ 300μSvy ⁻¹ (Arafa, 2004; UNSCEAR 2000)
4	Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR)	$ELCR \text{ (mSvy}^{-1}\text{)} = AEDE \text{ (mSvy}^{-1}\text{)} + LE(y) + RF$	0.29 x 10 ⁻³ (Ononugbo et al., 2015)
5	External Hazard Index (H _{ex})	$H_{ex} = C_{Ra}/370 + C_{Th}/259 + C_K/4810$	≤ 1 (UNSCEAR, 2000).
6	Internal Hazard Index (H _{in})	$H_{in} = C_{Ra}/185 + C_{Th}/259 + C_K/4810.$	≤ 1 (UNSCEAR, 2000).

CC -SvGy⁻¹Conversion Coefficient (0.7); TC – Time Conversion (8760); OF -Occupancy Factor (0.25); LE - Life Expectancy (55); RF -Risk Factor (0.05)

The background countrate has been evaluated when an empty sample container was counted in the same geometry as the standards for 18000s. The background countrate was subsequently subtracted from the sample countrate to obtain the net countrate, C_n before calculating the activity concentration of radionuclides in the samples (Righi *et al.*, 2009). The activity concentration A_c of radionuclide in an unknown sample of mass $m(s)$ is obtained using equation 1 below:

$$A_c = \frac{C_n}{\varepsilon(E)P_\gamma m(s)} \quad (1)$$

Where $\varepsilon(E)$ is the detector's efficiency for the specific gamma energy of interest (counts/Bq); P_γ is the probability of gamma emission for the specific radionuclide transition.

2.3 Radiological Health Hazard Indices

Six radiological hazards indices were used to assess the health hazards associated with public or occupational exposure within the three oilfield facilities with potential of an irradiated environment (Akhtar *et al.*, 2005) due to the presence of these chemicals and products. The indices and their computational models are presented in Table 3.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Activity Concentration of Radionuclide in Oilfield Chemicals and Products

The activity concentration of radionuclides in oilfield chemical and product samples determined using Thallium activated Sodium Iodide detector are presented in Tables 4a and 4b for activity concentration of radionuclides in solid and liquid samples respectively. Figures 2, 3 and 4 are comparison of the activity concentration of ^{40}K , ^{238}U , and ^{232}Th in solid samples with their UNSCEAR reference values. Figures 5, 6 and 7 are comparison of the activity concentration of ^{40}K , ^{238}U , and ^{232}Th in liquid samples with their UNSCEAR reference values.

3.2 Modelled Radiological Health Hazard Parameters

The radiological health hazard parameters from oilfield chemical and product samples are presented in Table 5a for solids and Table 5b for liquids. Absorbed dose rate (D), annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE), annual gonadal effective dose (AGED), excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR), external hazard index (Hex) and internal hazard index (Hin) are calculated from the samples radionuclides activity concentrations using their corresponding models from Table 3. Figures 8 and 9 are comparison of the ELCR in solid and liquid samples respectively with their UNSCEAR reference values.

4. DISCUSSION

The lowest to highest activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K , in solid samples are 0.03 ± 0.01 to $13.01 \pm 3.06 \text{ Bqkg}^{-1}$, 0.03 ± 0.003 to $1.17 \pm 0.09 \text{ Bqkg}^{-1}$ and 3.87 ± 0.31 to $20.64 \pm 7.71 \text{ Bqkg}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 4a). Also, the lowest to highest activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K , liquid samples are 0.31 ± 0.07 to $14.96 \pm 3.17 \text{ Bql}^{-1}$, 0.09 ± 0.01 to $2.19 \pm 0.16 \text{ Bql}^{-1}$ and, 0.22 ± 0.02 to $109.63 \pm 6.85 \text{ Bql}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 4b). Some activity concentrations were below detectable limits (BDL) due to the lower resolution of the NaI(Ti) detector used.

The result showed that higher activity concentration values of the radionuclide were obtained in liquid samples (Figures 5, 6 and 7) than the solid samples (Figures 2, 3 and 4). This is attributable to the fact that the solid samples (Barite, Bentonite, Blasting Grit, Class G Cement, coffee waste, Natural and Synthetic Polymers) are base materials extracted and used in semi-raw forms. Crude oil and condensate, although liquid samples have very low activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K as 2.35 ± 0.53 to $3.89 \pm 0.98 \text{ Bql}^{-1}$, 0.22 ± 0.02 to $0.37 \pm 0.03 \text{ Bql}^{-1}$ and 0.22 ± 0.02 to $7.19 \pm 0.53 \text{ Bql}^{-1}$ respectively, attributable to the treatment processes to enhance their market value.

Table 4a: Activity concentration of radionuclides determined from oilfield chemical and product - solid samples

S/N	Solid Samples (400mL)	Sample Code	K-40 (Bq/Kg)	U-238 (Bq/Kg)	Th-232 (Bq/Kg)
1	Bentonite 1A	BN _{1a}	17.23±1.25	4.66±1.04	0.49±0.04
2	Bentonite 1B	BN _{1b}	31.70±2.27	4.94±1.19	0.31±0.03
3	Bentonite 2A	BN _{2a}	32.70±2.22	5.54±1.31	0.59±0.05
4	Bentonite 2B	BN _{2b}	32.52±2.22	6.99±1.59	0.49±0.04
5	Barite 1A	BR _{1a}	17.34±1.14	0.38±0.10	0.25±0.02
6	Barite 1B	BR _{1b}	18.10±1.20	0.73±0.19	0.12±0.01
7	Barite 2A	BR _{2a}	15.66±1.07	2.84±0.65	0.10±0.01
8	Barite 2B	BR _{2b}	7.92±0.57	2.84±0.62	0.11±0.01
9	Class G cement 1A	CG _{1a}	26.54±1.77	2.65±0.64	0.20±0.02
10	Class G cement 1B	CG _{1b}	42.62±2.71	0.98±0.26	0.11±0.01
11	Class G cement 2A	CG _{2a}	16.87±1.20	1.17±0.28	0.27±0.02
12	Class G cement 2B	CG _{2b}	16.97±1.22	0.34±0.09	0.22±0.02
13	Blasting Grit 1A	BG _{1a}	31.37±2.03	3.81±0.81	0.22±0.02
14	Blasting Grit 1B	BG _{1b}	25.04±1.63	6.26±1.26	0.16±0.01
15	Blasting Grit 2A	BG _{2a}	31.89±2.01	4.34±0.92	0.14±0.01
16	Blasting Grit 2B	BG _{2b}	29.98 ± 1.89	4.47 ± 0.93	0.15 ± 0.01
17	Natural Polymer 1A	PN _{1a}	102.60±6.66	13.01±3.06	0.56±0.05
18	Natural Polymer 1B	PN _{1b}	99.25±6.25	0.03±0.01	0.56±0.05
19	Natural Polymer 2A	PN _{2a}	39.37 ± 2.55	BDL	0.29 ± 0.03
20	Natural Polymer 2B	PN _{2b}	120.64±7.71	6.56±1.75	0.55±0.01
21	Synthetic Polymer 1A	PS _{1a}	3.87±0.31	1.84±0.48	0.082±0.01
22	Synthetic Polymer 1B	PS _{1b}	9.46±0.75	5.28±1.23	0.09±0.01
23	Synthetic Polymer 2A	PS _{2a}	4.79±0.36	1.46±0.39	0.26±0.02
24	Synthetic Polymer 2B	PS _{2b}	14.89 ± 1.10	2.74 ± 0.71	0.03 ± 0.00
25	Produced Sediment 1A	TS _{1a}	9.48 ± 0.78	3.26 ± 0.82	1.17 ± 0.09
26	Produced Sediment 1B	TS _{1b}	28.98±2.19	3.45±0.87	0.89±0.07
27	Produced Sediment 2A	TS _{2a}	16.78 ± 1.28	2.91 ± 0.74	1.01 ± 0.08
28	Produced Sediment 2B	TS _{2b}	32.44 ± 2.38	8.61 ± 2.07	0.93 ± 0.07
29	Coffee Waste 1A	CW _{1a}	51.81±3.71	3.41±0.84	0.29±0.03
30	Coffee Waste 1B	CW _{1b}	46.26±3.41	7.32±1.68	0.36±0.03
31	Coffee Waste 2A	CW _{2a}	40.24±3.07	BDL	0.32±0.03
32	Coffee Waste 2B	CW _{2b}	33.34±7.59	2.57±0.22	BDL
UNSCEAR (2000)			400	35	30

BDL (Below Detectable Limit): Specific activity concentration of the radionuclide is below the minimum detectable activity (MDA)

Table 4b: Activity concentration of radionuclides determined from oilfield chemical and product - liquid samples

S/N	Liquid Samples (1L)	Sample Code	K-40 (Bq/L)	U-238 (Bq/L)	Th-232 (Bq/L)
1	Oil-Based mud	OB _m	17.57 ± 1.28	2.49 ± 0.64	0.31 ± 0.03
2	Produced Crude	PCr	0.22 ± 0.02	3.89 ± 0.98	0.37 ± 0.03
3	Produced Condensate	PCo	7.19 ± 0.53	2.35 ± 0.53	0.22 ± 0.02
4	Corrosion inhibitor 1	CI ₁	2.79 ± 0.21	1.81 ± 0.45	0.09 ± 0.01
5	Corrosion inhibitor 2	CI ₂	8.95 ± 0.71	4.00 ± 0.96	0.92 ± 0.01
6	Scale inhibitor (oil)	SIo	BDL	1.87 ± 0.48	0.26 ± 0.02
7	Scale inhibitor (water)1	SIw ₁	3.20 ± 0.24	0.57 ± 0.15	0.22 ± 0.02
8	Scale inhibitor (water)2	SIw ₂	86.20±5.70	7.73±2.02	1.84±0.14
9	Subsea Biocide 1	SB ₁	12.32±0.77	9.08±2.17	1.83±0.14
10	Subsea Biocide 2	SB ₂	99.06±6.20	14.96±3.17	2.19±0.16
11	Process Biocide 1	PB ₁	21.46 ± 1.55	2.09 ± 0.56	0.15 ± 0.01
12	Process Biocide 2	PB ₂	3.42±0.27	0.84±0.21	0.28±0.02
13	Diesel Biocide	DB	10.95 ± 0.84	0.31 ± 0.07	0.13 ± 0.01
14	Reverse Demulsifier	RD	108.83±6.84	6.60±1.76	1.91±0.14
15	Demulsifier	DM	20.91 ± 1.51	1.09 ± 0.29	0.32 ± 0.03
16	Oxygen Scavenger	OS	15.69 ± 0.97	BDL	0.21 ± 0.02
17	H ₂ S Scavenger	HS	109.63±6.85	8.61±2.07	0.93±0.07
18	Triethylene Glycol	TG	106.28±6.69	8.26±1.97	1.82±0.14
19	Acetic Acid	AA	4.50±0.34	4.05±0.97	0.14±0.01
20	Crude-Oil Defoamer	CD	6.99 ± 0.56	0.71 ± 0.18	0.23 ± 0.02
21	Chemical Solvent	CS	11.12±0.84	0.46±0.12	0.27±0.03
UNSCEAR (2000)			27.6	10	1

BDL (Below Detectable Limit): Specific activity concentration of the radionuclide is below the minimum detectable activity (MDA)

Five liquid samples that are production process chemicals (Reverse Demulsifier, Triethylene Glycol, Hydrogen Sulphide Scavenger, Subsea Biocide and Scale Inhibitor) showed significantly high activity concentrations (Figures 5, 6 and 7). Tables 4a and 4b show that their activity concentration values for 40K ranged from 86.20±5.70 to 109.63±6.85 BqL⁻¹; also values for 238U ranged from 6.60±1.76 to 14.96±3.17 BqL⁻¹; and values for 232Th ranged from 0.93±0.07 to 2.19±0.16 BqL⁻¹, significantly higher than UNSCEAR standard values of 27.6 BqL⁻¹ for 40K, 10BqL⁻¹ for 238U and 1BqL⁻¹ for 232Th. This is attributable to the fact that the salts of the radionuclides are concentrated during the manufacturing processes of these five liquid samples.

Table 5a and Table 5b show that radiological health hazard parameters obtained from the solid and liquid samples analysis respectively, are consistently lower than UNSCEAR values. The Absorbed Dose Rate, AEDE, AGED and ELCR obtained ranged from 8.308 to 12.402 nGyh⁻¹, 0.013 to 0.19 mSvy⁻¹, 3.686 to 113.76 μSvy⁻¹ and 0.045 to 0.067x10⁻³, which are consistently lower than UNSCEAR limits: 57nGyh⁻¹, 1mSvy⁻¹, 300 μSvy⁻¹ and 0.29x10⁻³ respectively.

Fig. 2: ⁴⁰K Activity Concentration in Oilfield Solid Samples

Fig. 3: ²³⁸U Activity Concentration in Oilfield Solid Samples

Fig. 4: ²³²Th Activity Concentration in Oilfield Solid Samples

Fig. 5: ⁴⁰K Activity Concentration in Oilfield Liquid Samples

Fig. 6: ²³⁸U Activity Concentration in Oilfield Liquid Samples

Fig. 7: ²³²Th Activity Concentration in Oilfield Liquid Samples

Table 5a: Comparison of the radiological hazard indices from oilfield chemical and product Solid samples

S/N	Solid Samples (400mL)	Sample Code	D (nGy/h)	AEDE (mSv/y)	AGED (μ Sv/y)	ELCR $\times 10^{-3}$	Hex	Hin
1	Bentonite 1A	BN _{1a}	3.176	0.005	21.858	0.017	0.018	0.031
2	Bentonite 1B	BN _{1b}	3.797	0.006	26.514	0.020	0.021	0.034
3	Bentonite 2A	BN _{2a}	4.289	0.007	29.853	0.023	0.024	0.039
4	Bentonite 2B	BN _{2b}	4.890	0.007	33.859	0.026	0.028	0.046
5	Barite 1A	BR _{1a}	1.054	0.002	7.664	0.006	0.006	0.007
6	Barite 1B	BR _{1b}	1.167	0.002	8.441	0.006	0.006	0.008
7	Barite 2A	BR _{2a}	2.027	0.003	14.111	0.011	0.011	0.019
8	Barite 2B	BR _{2b}	1.711	0.003	11.722	0.009	0.010	0.017
9	Class G cement 1A	CG _{1a}	2.455	0.004	17.358	0.013	0.013	0.021
10	Class G cement 1B	CG _{1b}	2.298	0.004	16.871	0.012	0.012	0.015
11	Class G cement 2A	CG _{2a}	1.412	0.002	10.041	0.008	0.008	0.011
12	Class G cement 2B	CG _{2b}	1.001	0.002	7.299	0.005	0.005	0.006
13	Blasting Grit 1A	BG _{1a}	3.205	0.005	22.543	0.017	0.018	0.028
14	Blasting Grit 1B	BG _{1b}	4.036	0.006	27.875	0.022	0.023	0.040
15	Blasting Grit 2A	BG _{2a}	3.422	0.005	24.009	0.018	0.019	0.031
16	Blasting Grit 2B	BG _{2b}	3.408	0.005	23.853	0.018	0.019	0.031
17	Natural Polymer 1A	PN _{1a}	10.637	0.016	74.758	0.057	0.059	0.094
18	Natural Polymer 1B	PN _{1b}	4.500	0.007	33.598	0.024	0.023	0.023
19	Natural Polymer 2A	PN _{2a}	1.822	0.003	13.574	0.010	0.009	0.009
20	Natural Polymer 2B	PN _{2b}	8.403	0.013	60.450	0.045	0.045	0.063
21	Synthetic Polymer 1A	PS _{1a}	1.062	0.002	7.244	0.006	0.006	0.011
22	Synthetic Polymer 1B	PS _{1b}	2.890	0.004	19.662	0.016	0.017	0.031
23	Synthetic Polymer 2A	PS _{2a}	1.036	0.002	7.102	0.006	0.006	0.010
24	Synthetic Polymer 2B	PS _{2b}	1.905	0.003	13.267	0.010	0.011	0.018
25	Produced Sediment 1A	TS _{1a}	2.628	0.004	17.941	0.014	0.015	0.024
26	Produced Sediment 1B	TS _{1b}	3.355	0.005	23.480	0.018	0.019	0.028
27	Produced Sediment 2A	TS _{2a}	2.671	0.004	18.483	0.014	0.015	0.023
28	Produced Sediment 2B	TS _{2b}	5.908	0.009	40.678	0.032	0.034	0.057
29	Coffee Waste 1A	CW _{1a}	3.916	0.006	28.017	0.021	0.021	0.030
30	Coffee Waste 1B	CW _{1b}	5.534	0.008	38.649	0.030	0.031	0.051
31	Coffee Waste 2A	CW _{2a}	1.877	0.003	13.973	0.010	0.010	0.010
32	Coffee Waste 2B	CW _{2b}	16.999	0.026	113.76	0.091	0.100	0.190
	UNSCEAR (2000)		57	1	300	0.29	1	1

Table 5b: Comparison of the radiological hazard indices from oilfield chemical and product liquid samples

S/N	Liquid Samples (1L)	Sample Code	D (nGy/h)	AEDE (mSv/y)	AGED (μSv/y)	ELCR x10 ⁻³	Hex	Hin
1	Oil-Based mud	Obm	2.076	0.003	14.507	0.011	0.012	0.018
2	Produced Crude	PCr	2.036	0.003	13.636	0.011	0.012	0.023
3	Produced Condensate	PCo	1.522	0.002	10.439	0.008	0.009	0.015
4	Corrosion inhibitor 1	CI ₁	1.008	0.002	6.845	0.005	0.006	0.011
5	Corrosion inhibitor 2	CI ₂	2.793	0.004	19.016	0.015	0.016	0.027
6	Scale inhibitor (oil)	SI _o	1.025	0.002	6.865	0.006	0.006	0.011
7	Scale inhibitor (water)1	SI _{w1}	0.533	0.001	3.686	0.003	0.003	0.005
8	Scale inhibitor (water)2	SI _{w2}	8.308	0.013	58.644	0.045	0.046	0.067
9	Subsea Biocide 1	SB ₁	5.845	0.009	39.575	0.031	0.034	0.059
10	Subsea Biocide 2	SB ₂	12.402	0.019	86.485	0.067	0.069	0.110
11	Process Biocide1	PB ₁	1.954	0.003	13.824	0.010	0.011	0.016
12	Process Biocide2	PB ₂	0.705	0.001	4.840	0.004	0.004	0.006
13	Diesel Biocide	DB	0.681	0.001	4.940	0.004	0.004	0.004
14	Reverse Demulsifier	RD	8.774	0.013	62.550	0.047	0.048	0.066
15	Demulsifier	DM	1.574	0.002	11.271	0.008	0.009	0.011
16	Oxygen Scavenger	OS	0.785	0.001	5.804	0.004	0.004	0.004
17	H ₂ S Scavenger	HS	9.127	0.014	64.916	0.049	0.050	0.073
18	Triethylene Glycol	TG	9.378	0.014	66.503	0.050	0.051	0.074
19	Acetic Acid	AA	2.146	0.003	14.513	0.012	0.012	0.023
20	Crude-Oil Defoamer	CD	0.762	0.001	5.350	0.004	0.004	0.006
21	Chemical Solvent	CS	0.844	0.001	6.042	0.005	0.005	0.006
	UNSCEAR (2000)		57	1	300	0.29	1	1

CONCLUSION

The oilfield chemicals and products were successfully analyzed for radioactive elements using Thallium activated Sodium Iodide detector. The result clearly shows that the radioactivity levels in all solid and some liquid samples are generally below the limits set by UNSCEAR but within the range found in similar studies. The Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR) for solid samples (Figure 8), and for liquid samples (Figure 9) are also well below UNSCEAR limits.

However, five productions chemicals that are liquid samples were identified to show radioactivity levels that exceed limits set by UNSCEAR indicating some level of radiological contamination. Their direct contact to the skin of oilfield workers is considered detrimental to their health and their discharge into water bodies could lead to contaminations of aquifer used for drinking within the locality due to the elevated activity concentrations above limits, although their radiological health hazard indices calculated remain consistently lower than UNSCEAR, ICRP and IAEA standard values. The result of this work revealed that Reverse Demulsifier, Triethylene Glycol, Hydrogen Sulphide Scavenger, Subsea Biocide and Scale Inhibitor commonly used in the oilfield treatment processes of crude oil and condensates are associated with high levels of ionizing radiation that may be unsafe to people and the environment.

We conclude therefore that if no remedial steps are implemented, there will be long-term risks to health of the workers handling and managing the storage of these oilfield chemicals, and inhabitants of the host areas prone to discharges. Such remedial steps could include implementation of radiation management controls for the chemicals and dosimetry monitoring for the workers.

Fig. 8: Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk due to Oilfield Solid Samples

Fig. 9: Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk due to Oilfield Liquid Samples

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